

Financial Literacy and Sustainability of Table Banking Projects Among Mixed Gender Self-Help Groups in Maralal Ward Samburu County Kenya

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Abstract

Despite the availability of multiple bursary programs in Maralal Ward, significant challenges undermine their effectiveness. The study examined the influence of project leadership management practices on the Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students in Maralal Ward, Samburu County, Kenya. The specific objective assessed the influence of project decision integration on the Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students in Maralal Ward in Samburu County, Kenya. The study was anchored on Ethical Leadership Theory and Stakeholder Theory. Convergent parallel design was adopted. The study targeted a population of 2,381 students, 24 school administrators and 6 pivotal bursary committee members, and leaders serving as key informants. A sample of 343 respondents were selected using stratified sampling technique. Data was collected using questionnaires and key informant interviews. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Qualitative data from interviews were analyzed thematically. Findings were presented using tables. Data were collected from 280 respondents. Key findings indicated that bursary programs in Maralal Ward moderately integrated project decisions, with needy considerations and management awareness rated highly ($M = 3.54$), but weak adherence to standards ($M = 2.72$), inconsistent ethical compliance ($M = 3.29$), and limited training ($M = 3.38$). On performance, bursaries improved student retention ($M = 3.76$), transition ($M = 3.60$), academic outcomes ($M = 3.54$), and enrolment ($M = 3.48$), with funds largely used appropriately ($M = 3.55$). However, delays in disbursement ($M = 2.83$) and low stakeholder satisfaction ($M = 2.83$) remained key challenges, despite sustainability strategies in place ($M = 3.70$). Qualitative evidence reinforced that timely and adequate bursary support is critical to student success. The study recommend that the program should strengthen ethical standards and decision-making guidelines to improve stakeholder satisfaction and maximize student outcomes.

Keywords: Project leadership management practices, Performance of Bursary Programs, Needy Secondary School Students, project decision integration.

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INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

Bursary schemes aim to increase secondary education access, equity, and retention by assisting financially disadvantaged students, particularly those living in marginalized areas (Mwangi, 2023). They seek to minimize financial barriers, which frequently result in low enrollment, high dropout rates, and incomplete education. When properly administered, bursary programs increase educational continuity, improve transition to higher levels, and eliminate disparities in learning possibilities (Oduor, 2024).

This ideal, however, has not been fully realized in Maralal Ward, Samburu County, where many bursary programs confront obstacles such as insufficient funding, irregular disbursements, and poor beneficiary targeting. According to the Samburu County Education Office (2024), a considerable proportion of disadvantaged students continue to drop out or have their education stopped as a result of delayed or insufficient bursary disbursements. For example, most beneficiaries receive as little as KSh 2,000, which is significantly less than actual school fee requirements, resulting in recurrent arrears and eventual absenteeism. Weak monitoring methods, political involvement, and a lack of accountability in bursary distribution all reduce program efficacy (Nyangena & Kariuki, 2023).

Although bursary support is widely acknowledged as a vital strategy for enhancing educational performance in underserved communities (Kimani, 2022), many students in Maralal Ward

continue to be denied meaningful access due to systemic inefficiencies. Some well-managed bursary programs in other counties have shown positive results by lowering dropout rates, boosting enrollment, and improving completion rates (Otieno, 2021; Cheruiyot, 2023), but these are the exceptions. In Maralal Ward, chronic challenges of injustice, misallocation, and inadequate governance continue to impede the implementation of bursaries as a tool for promoting educational equity.

With a focus on project decision integration this study investigated the influence of project leadership management practices on the Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students in Maralal Ward, Samburu County, contributing new empirical evidence to education policy and program implementation discourse in Kenya.

This study examined the influence of project leadership management practices on the effectiveness of bursary programs for underprivileged secondary school students in Maralal Ward, Samburu County, with a particular emphasis on decision integration. While bursary systems were implemented in Kenya to improve educational equity, access, and retention, their success has frequently been undermined by weak leadership structures, fragmented decision-making, and insufficient stakeholder involvement (Lengoiboni, 2022). Decision integration, defined as the synchronization of planning, resource allocation, and stakeholder input within program management, has been demonstrated to increase transparency, accountability, and efficiency in project implementation (Mwangi & Kimathi, 2023; Odhiambo, 2024).

Despite this, little research has explicitly related decision integration within project leadership techniques to the effectiveness of bursary programs in marginalized environments like Samburu County, where financial exclusion and dropout rates remain high. This study intended to address this gap by looking into how integrated decision-making affects bursary program outcomes. The findings were expected to help policymakers, education administrators, and local leaders improve bursary management systems, promoting equal access, retention, and completion among Kenya's underprivileged secondary school students.

This study is based on Ethical Leadership Theory and Stakeholder Theory, which together provide a complete lens for investigating how leadership practices affect the success of bursary programs for underprivileged secondary school students in Maralal Ward, Samburu County.

Brown et al. (2005) developed Ethical Leadership Theory, which stresses leaders' roles in fostering ethical behavior through personal acts and interpersonal interactions. Recent research has demonstrated the importance of ethical leadership in improving organizational outcomes. For example, Malik et al. (2023) found that ethical leadership promotes trust and collaboration among team members, resulting in higher performance. Similarly, Kandasamy (2024) explains how ethical leadership is critical in navigating the problems of artificial intelligence, emphasizing the significance of fairness, openness, and sustainability in leadership practices.

In the context of bursary programs, ethical leadership ensures that resource allocation and stakeholder involvement decisions are handled in an honest and equitable manner. This strategy not only improves openness and accountability, but it also aligns the program's aims with the needs and expectations of the community, resulting in increased overall effectiveness.

Stakeholder Theory, proposed by Freeman (1984), holds that organizations should consider the interests and needs of all stakeholders in their decision-making processes. Recent implementations of this idea in education have demonstrated its importance in supporting sustainable development and inclusive decision-making. Peng et al. (2024) conducted a review of the implementation of stakeholder theory in education, emphasizing the significance of engaging multiple stakeholders to achieve sustainable goals. Furthermore, Valentinov's (2023) research investigates the convergence of stakeholder theory and institutional economics, providing insights into how stakeholder engagement might address complex organizational difficulties.

Using Stakeholder Theory in bursary programs entails identifying and engaging important stakeholders such as students, parents, teachers, and community leaders to ensure that the program meets their various needs and expectations. This inclusive approach creates stakeholder ownership and accountability, resulting in more effective and sustainable program performance. This study, which combines Ethical Leadership Theory with Stakeholder Theory, provides a strong framework for investigating how leadership practices and stakeholder participation influence the performance of bursary programs. The combination of ethical decision-making and inclusive stakeholder involvement is thought to improve the openness, accountability, and overall success of these programs, encouraging equitable access to education for low-income secondary school children in Samburu County.

Decision integration has emerged as a critical driver of effectiveness and sustainability in bursary programs for needy secondary school students. According to Zhang, Lee, Ali, DiPaola, Cheng, and Breazeal (2023), decision integration encompasses the coordination of planning, resource allocation, and stakeholder engagement to make consistent, fair, and transparent decisions. In the context of bursary programs, decision integration equips administrators and committees with competencies such as ethical reasoning, stakeholder consultation, monitoring, and reflective evaluation, which collectively enhance program performance and credibility.

Globally, research shows that programs employing integrated decision-making processes are better able to allocate resources efficiently, maintain transparency, and minimize biases, thereby improving overall program outcomes (Lim, 2024; Wexler & Specker Sullivan, 2023). The effectiveness of bursary programs depend not only on the availability of financial resources but also on the integration of decision-making processes, ethical principles, and operational frameworks. Programs that incorporate decision integration ensure that selection processes are fair, transparent, and responsive to the needs of disadvantaged students. For instance, studies in Malaysia and Zimbabwe show that ethical and integrated decision-making mechanisms significantly enhanced program accountability and targeted support to eligible students (Yusof et al., 2020; Kanengoni, 2021).

At the regional level, particularly within Sub-Saharan Africa, decision integration has been linked to improved performance and credibility of educational support programs. Gumede et al. (2021) reported that South African bursary programs that embedded ethical awareness into decision-making improved students' critical thinking, resource ethics, and academic outcomes. Similarly, Mokadem et al. (2025) and Msuya (2022) highlight that Tanzanian and Algerian programs adopting integrated decision systems strengthened students' accountability, moral reasoning, and program participation. These studies show that combining decision integration with continuous monitoring and ethical reflection fosters program resilience and equitable access.

In Kenya, empirical research has demonstrated the importance of decision integration in bursary management. Paul (2020) found that incorporating ethical and coordinated decision processes in Baringo County enhanced fairness in fund distribution. Irungu (2020) reported that Kirinyaga County administrators using structured decision integration achieved unbiased allocation and improved program outcomes. Embu County implemented well-defined decision and ethical

criteria to minimize mismanagement and corruption (Mbogo, 2023; Ojwang, 2022), while Uasin Gishu County adopted continuous reflective evaluation to improve program alignment and student support (Rahama, 2024; Chelulei, 2021).

Across global, regional, and national literature, three key gaps emerge: first, an empirical gap in measuring decision integration as a distinct contributor to bursary program performance; second, a conceptual gap in linking integrated decision-making directly to student outcomes; and third, a methodological gap, as most studies rely on cross-sectional designs, limiting longitudinal insights. This study addresses these gaps by focusing explicitly on decision integration, examining its role in coordinating ethical, stakeholder-informed decisions, and employing both qualitative and quantitative methods to capture its impact on bursary program performance in Samburu County, Kenya.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research design is a strategy plan that defines the most relevant approaches, instruments, and strategies to achieve the study objectives (Leavy, 2022). In this study, a convergent parallel design was used, which allowed for the simultaneous collection of quantitative and qualitative data. This methodology made it easier to compare and combine findings from both methodologies, allowing for a more thorough investigation of how decision integration and ethical leadership affect bursary program performance. The study created a strong and balanced picture of program dynamics, problems, and triumphs by combining numerical data with qualitative observations.

The target population consisted of people who possessed the traits required to achieve the study's aims. The study focused on 2,381 less fortunate students attending secondary schools in Maralal Ward who were identified through bursary application records. These students, who had previously requested financial aid, were chosen to investigate how leadership and decision integration affected their educational opportunities and outcomes.

In addition, the study targeted 24 school administrators from all public secondary schools in Maralal Ward, as well as six key bursary committee members and leaders. School administrators served as liaisons between students and bursary committees, giving crucial information on program implementation and student needs. Bursary committee members and leaders oversaw

fund allocation and provided insights into ethical issues, decision-making procedures, and the problems of guaranteeing openness and equity in fund distribution.

The relevant research ethics committee approved the project, and the Samburu County Government provided extra authorization. All participants gave their informed consent, with additional measures in place for vulnerable populations to ensure voluntary participation. Confidentiality and anonymity were preserved, and data were securely retained, with findings provided aggregated to protect participant names.

A research study uses a subset known as sample size to conclude the population (Lakens, 2022). The dimensions of the research sample determine how well study outcomes represent reality alongside reliability and accuracy levels (Lakens, 2022). For the quantitative strand, the sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula for finite populations at a 95% confidence level and a $\pm 5\%$ precision margin.

Thus, a sample of 343 needy students was drawn. To ensure fair representation across school types, Probability Proportionate to Size (PPS) sampling was applied to allocate the sample proportionally among mixed-day, boys-only, and girls-only schools. Within each stratum, respondents were then selected through simple random sampling to minimize bias and enhance representativeness. For the qualitative strand, purposive sampling was employed to identify six key informants comprising all 24 school administrators (principals/teachers) and six bursary committee leaders, including the chairperson. These informants were targeted for their ability to provide rich, context-specific insights into decision integration, transparency, and ethical considerations in bursary allocation. This combination of sampling methods ensured both statistical generalizability in the quantitative findings and contextual depth in the qualitative narratives, consistent with the logic of the convergent parallel design.

According to Pandey and Pandey (2021), the choice of data collection instruments is central to ensuring that research questions and hypotheses are addressed with accuracy and reliability. This study employed a mixed-methods approach, using structured questionnaires for quantitative data and Key Informant Interview (KII) guides for qualitative insights. Structured questionnaires are cost-effective, allow efficient data collection, and enhance comparability across respondents

(Alam, 2021). The KII guides, on the other hand, provided an avenue for in-depth exploration of stakeholders' perspectives on the management and performance of bursary programs (Ojurongbe & Tirol, 2023).

Prior to fieldwork, the researcher obtained an approval letter from the Catholic University of Eastern Africa, a research permit from the National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI), and authorization from the Samburu County Director of Education. This was followed by pre-visits to Maralal Ward to organize logistics, coordinate with school administrators, and book appointments with key informants. Questionnaires were distributed to sampled students during scheduled school visits, while face-to-face interviews with key informants were conducted separately then the findings were merged for general conclusion.

The quantitative strand's data were entered, reviewed, and cleaned using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. Descriptive statistics, such as means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages, were used to summarize participants' responses. To test study hypotheses and investigate variable correlations, inferential statistics were used. These methods included chi-square tests, correlation analysis, and multiple regression. The regression model was very effective for determining the combined and individual effects of predictor variables on bursary program performance. The statistical significance thresholds were utilized to decide whether to accept or reject the null hypotheses (Lakens, 2022).

For the qualitative strand, interview data were examined for completeness, coherence, and relevance to the study's aims. A thematic analysis approach was used to discover patterns, categories, and themes in the participants' tales. To deepen and contextualize the quantitative data, insights were given using verbatim quotations that captured respondents' lived experiences, views, and opinions (Braun & Clarke, 2022; Nowell & Albrecht, 2023). This mixed-methods approach maintained both statistical rigor and contextual depth, resulting in a comprehensive knowledge of the determinants driving bursary program performance (Creswell & Creswell, 2023).

FINDINGS, INTERPRETATIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

Project leadership approaches are increasingly acknowledged as a critical factor influencing the efficacy and sustainability of social development projects, particularly those aimed at

disadvantaged groups. In the context of bursary programs, leadership decisions about integration, accountability, and stakeholder involvement have a direct impact on resource distribution equity and intervention success. Recent studies highlight that ethical and inclusive leadership practices foster transparency, enhance trust among stakeholders, and improve program outcomes (Mansaray, 2022; Amjad & Awan, 2023). Bursary programs play an important role in providing education to impoverished secondary school students in Kenya, but difficulties of equity, resource adequacy, and administrative inefficiencies persist (Njeru & Waweru, 2023).

Project Decision Integration and Performance of Bursary Programs

This section focuses on the findings related to project decision integration in the management of bursary programs, in fulfillment of assessing the influence of project decision integration on the performance of bursary programs for needy secondary school students in Maralal Ward, Samburu County. Decision integration is a critical aspect of project leadership, as it ensures that multiple perspectives are considered, stakeholders are actively engaged, and decisions are made in a structured and transparent manner. Effective decision integration contributes to the equitable allocation of bursary funds, enhances accountability, and promotes program efficiency.

Data on project decision integration was collected using structured questionnaires with items measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree) administered to bursary beneficiaries. Additional qualitative insights were obtained through key informant interviews to capture deeper perspectives on decision-making practices within the bursary programs. The descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, mean scores, and standard deviations for each decision integration item, are presented in the table below.

Table 1: Project Decision Integration

Statements (Project decision integration)	Std % F	D % F	N % F	A % F	SA % F	Mean	Std Dvt
Needy considerations are fully integrated into the decision-making processes for bursary fund distribution.	42 (16.8%)	49 (19.6%)	0 (0%)	50 (20%)	109 (43.6%)	3.54	1.59
The integration of project decisions on management helps ensure fairness in supervision of funds distribution.	48 (19.2%)	51 (20.4%)	0 (0%)	105 (42%)	46 (18.4%)	3.20	1.44

Bursary fund administrators adhere to clear standards in their decision-making and making the correct decision about the project integration	98 (39.2%)	37 (14.8%)	3 (1.2%)	62 (24.8%)	50 (20%)	2.72	1.64
Bursary fund administrators do not adhere to clear ethical standards in their decision-making	47 (18.8%)	45 (18%)	0 (0%)	105 (42%)	53 (21.2%)	3.29	1.45
The bursary fund management team demonstrates a strong awareness of project integration issues related to fund allocation.	51 (20.4%)	37 (14.8%)	0 (0%)	49 (19.6%)	113 (45.2%)	3.54	1.63
Project integration is not emphasized in the training and development of those responsible for managing bursary funds.	36 (14.4%)	46 (18.4%)	3 (1.2%)	118 (47.2%)	47 (18.8%)	3.38	1.36
Overall composite Mean and standard deviation						3.29	1.74

Based on the findings, needy considerations are fully integrated into the decision-making processes for bursary fund distribution had a mean score of 3.45 and a standard deviation of 1.59. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 42(16.8%) strongly disagreed, 49(19.6%) disagreed, 0(0%) were neutral, 50(20%) agreed, and 109(43.6%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.54 is higher than the overall mean of 3.29. The implication of these findings in this statement is, during the decision- making process for bursary allocation, needy considerations are fully integrated. The Standard Deviation of 1.59 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.74, indicating convergence of opinions of the respondents.

The responses on, the integration of project decisions on management helps ensure fairness in supervision of funds distribution had a mean score of 3.20 and a standard deviation of 1.44. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 48(19.2%) strongly disagreed, 51(20.4%) disagreed, 0(0%) were neutral, 105(42%) agreed, and 46(18.4%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.20 is lower than the overall mean of 3.29. The implication of these findings in this statement is, fairness in the distribution of funds is witnessed due to the integration of project decisions. The Standard Deviation of 1.44 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.74, indicating agreeing opinions of the respondents.

The responses on, bursary fund administrators adhere to clear standards in their decision-making and making the correct decision about the project integration had a mean score of 2.72 and a

standard deviation of 1.64. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 98(39.2%) strongly disagreed, 37(14.8%) disagreed, 3(24.8%) were neutral, 62(24.8%) agreed, and 50(20%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 2.72 is lower than the overall mean of 3.29. The implication of these findings is, bursary fund administrators don't adhere to clear standards in their decision making hence making wrong decisions about the project integration. The Standard Deviation of 1.64 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.74, indicating agreeing opinions of the respondents.

The responses on bursary fund administrators do not adhere to clear ethical standards in their decision-making had a mean score of 3.29 and a standard deviation of 1.45. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 47(18.8%) strongly disagreed, 45(20%) disagreed, 0(105%) were neutral, 105(42%) agreed, and 53(21.2%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.29 is at par with the overall mean of 3.29. The implication of these findings is, the administrators do not adhere to the clear ethical standards in decision making. The Standard Deviation of 1.45 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.74, indicating agreeing opinions of the respondents.

The responses on the bursary fund management team demonstrates a strong awareness of project integration issues related to fund allocation had a mean score of 3.54 and a standard deviation of 1.63. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 51(20.4%) strongly disagreed, 37(14.8%) disagreed, 0(0%) were neutral, 49(19.6%) agreed, and 113(45.2%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.54 is higher than the overall mean of 3.29. The implication of these findings is, the management team demonstrates a strong awareness of project integration issues related to fund allocation. The Standard Deviation of 1.63 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.74, indicating agreeing opinions of the respondents.

In the statement, project integration is not emphasized in the training and development of those responsible for managing bursary funds had a mean score of 3.38 and a standard deviation of 1.36. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 36(14.4%) strongly disagreed, 46(18.4%) disagreed, 3(1.2%) were neutral, 118(47.2%) agreed, and 47(18.8%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.38 is higher than the overall mean of 3.29. These findings imply that Project integration is not emphasized in the training and development of those

responsible for managing bursary funds. The Standard Deviation of 1.36 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.74, indicating agreeing opinions of the respondents.

Qualitative Data on Project decision integration and Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students

It was discovered that Accountability of the Bursary Fund and Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students existed, related to the answers given to the assertions provided at each variable in the interview guide questions. The qualitative responses are summarized,

“There’s a strong link. When the bursary is sufficient and paid on time, the students remain in school and concentrate on their studies. Otherwise, many miss classes due to fee arrears or transfer to cheaper schools with fewer resources. Regular reviews of student needs and a better tracking system of bursary impact would make the program more effective,” KII-Respondent 6

Discussions on Project Decision Integration and Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students

Active ethical standards development leads to transparent operational frameworks that build accountable relationships among all stakeholders (Zhang, Lee, Ali, DiPaola, Cheng & Breazeal, 2023). Through continuous ethical reflection, administrators can monitor the program's effects to ensure alignment between its core mission and objectives. The Chinese educational system proves effective through previous experience analysis thus enabling administrators to improve student support approaches. Through this flexible and engaged approach government managers establish trust and credibility and maintain program effectiveness throughout time (Zhao et al., 2022).

Ethical standards represent an essential foundation required for maintaining just bursary program administration which is shown through Zambian studies (Kabwe, 2022). To minimize corruption and favoritism defenders of bursary programs need policy frameworks that detail clear eligibility terms and precise application paths and funding distribution structures. These accountability measures establish fairness in student selection, which ensures funding reaches students who deserve it most, and enhances the positive results of these programs.

Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students

There were six statements that were addressed, as shown in Table 4.8, related to the Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students on project leadership management practices and performance of bursary programs for needy secondary school students in Maralal ward, Samburu County, Kenya.

Table 2: Performance of Bursary Programs for Needy Secondary School Students

Statements (Performance of Bursary Programs)	Std % F	D % F	N % F	A % F	SA % F	Mean	Std Dvt
Bursary programs have contributed to a higher retention rate of students in secondary schools.	37 (14.8%)	38 (15.2%)	0 (0%)	49 (19.6%)	126 (50.4%)	3.76	1.54
The bursary fund significantly improves the transition of students from one educational level to the next due to continued support from the bursary kit	40 (16%)	48 (19.2%)	6 (2.4%)	35 (14%)	121 (48.4%)	3.60	1.60
The overall satisfaction with the bursary program is high among all stakeholders involved.	35 (14%)	118 (47.2%)	0 (0%)	49 (19.6%)	48 (19.2%)	2.83	1.40
Bursary funds are disbursed to students promptly, ensuring no delays in payment to align with the school's fee payment schedules.	41 (16.4%)	109 (43.6%)	0 (0%)	52 (20.8%)	48 (19.2%)	2.83	1.43
The availability of bursaries has increased the number of students enrolling in secondary education.	53 (21.2%)	39 (15.6%)	4 (1.6%)	44 (17.6%)	110 (44%)	3.48	1.65
The funds allocated through the bursary scheme are adequately used for school fees and other essential school-related costs.	39 (15.6%)	52 (20.8%)	3 (1.2%)	45 (18%)	111 (44.4%)	3.55	1.58
Students who receive bursary funds show improved academic	53 (21.2%)	37 (14.8%)	0 (0%)	41 (16.4%)	119 (47.6%)	3.54	1.66

performance compared to those who do not receive the support							
There are clear strategies in place to ensure the long-term sustainability of bursary funds.	12 (4.8%)	59 (23.6%)	4 (1.6%)	92 (36.8%)	83 (33.2%)	3.70	1.28
Overall composite Mean and standard deviation						3.44	1.56

Based on the findings, bursary programs have contributed to a higher retention rate of students in secondary schools had a mean score of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 1.54. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 37(14.8%) strongly disagreed, 38(15.2%) disagreed, 0(0%) were neutral, 49(19.6%) agreed, and 126(50.4%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.76 is higher than the overall mean of 3.44. The implication of these findings in this statement is that it's very true that bursary programs have really contributed to higher retention of students in secondary schools. The Standard Deviation of 1.54 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.56, indicating convergence of opinions of the respondents.

The responses on, the bursary fund significantly improves the transition of students from one educational level to the next due to continued support from the bursary kit had a mean score of 3.60 and a standard deviation of 1.60. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 40(16%) strongly disagreed, 48(19.2%) disagreed, 6(2.4%) were neutral, 35(14%) agreed, and 121(48.4%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.60 is higher than the overall mean of 3.44. The implication of these findings in this statement is, due to the continued support from the bursary kit, it has been very easy for students to transition from one educational level to the next. The Standard Deviation of 1.60 is higher than the overall standard deviation of 1.56, indicating disagreeing opinions of the respondents.

The responses on, the overall satisfaction with the bursary program is high among all stakeholders involved had a mean score of 2.83 and a standard deviation of 1.40. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 35(14%) strongly disagreed, 118(47.2%) disagreed, 0(0%) were neutral, 49(19.6%) agreed, and 48(19.2%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 2.83 is lower than the overall mean of 3.44. The implication of these findings is, satisfaction from all

the stakeholders isn't that satisfactory. The Standard Deviation of 1.40 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.56, indicating agreeing opinions of the respondents.

The responses on, Bursary funds are disbursed to students promptly, ensuring no delays in payment to align with the school's fee payment schedules had a mean score of 2.83 and a standard deviation of 1.43. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 41(16.4%) strongly disagreed, 109(43.6%) disagreed, 0(0%) were neutral, 52(20.8%) agreed, and 48(19.2%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 2.83 is lower than the overall mean of 3.44. The implication of these findings is, delays are witnessed in payment of students to the school due to the bursary fund not disbursed promptly. The Standard Deviation of 1.43 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.56, indicating agreeing opinions of the respondents.

The responses on, the availability of bursaries has increased the number of students enrolling in secondary education had a mean score of 3.48 and a standard deviation of 1.65. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 53(21.2%) strongly disagreed, 39(15.6%) disagreed, 4(1.6%) were neutral, 44(17.6%) agreed, and 110(44%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.48 is higher than the overall mean of 3.44. The implication of these findings is, due to the availability of bursaries, number of students enrolling in secondary education. The Standard Deviation of 1.65 is higher than the overall standard deviation of 1.56, indicating disagreeing opinions of the respondents.

In the statement, the funds allocated through the bursary scheme are adequately used for school fees and other essential school-related costs, had a mean score of 3.55 and a standard deviation of 1.58. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 39(15.6%) strongly disagreed, 52(20.8%) disagreed, 3(1.2%) were neutral, 45(18%) agreed, and 111(44.4%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.55 is higher than the overall mean of 3.44. These findings imply that fees and other essential school related costs are adequate enough from the bursary allocated. The Standard Deviation of 1.58 is higher than the overall standard deviation of 1.56, indicating disagreeing opinions of the respondents.

In the statement, Students who receive bursary funds show improved academic performance compared to those who do not receive the support, had a mean score of 3.54 and a standard deviation of 1.66. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 53(21.2%) strongly

disagreed, 37(14.8%) disagreed, 0(0%) were neutral, 41(16.4%) agreed, and 119(47.6%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.54 is higher than the overall mean of 3.44. These findings imply good academic performance is seen from the students who have received bursary funds compared to the ones who do not receive any funds. The Standard Deviation of 1.66 is higher than the overall standard deviation of 1.56, indicating disagreeing opinions of the respondents.

In the statement, there are clear strategies in place to ensure the long-term sustainability of bursary funds, had a mean score of 3.70 and a standard deviation of 1.28. Data collected from 250 respondents revealed that 12(4.8%) strongly disagreed, 59(23.6%) disagreed, 4(1.6%) were neutral, 92(36.8%) agreed, and 83(33.2%) strongly agreed. These findings indicate that the mean of 3.70 is higher than the overall mean of 3.44. These findings imply that strategies have been put in place to ensure long-term sustainability of bursary funds. The Standard Deviation of 1.28 is lower than the overall standard deviation of 1.56, indicating agreeing opinions of the respondents.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concluded that successful project decision integration has a substantial impact on the performance of bursary programs for needy secondary school students in Maralal Ward, Samburu County, Kenya. Bursary fund adequacy guarantees a clear distribution of money to all needy students and favourably helps to the allocation of bursary project funds. Adequate public awareness of bursary money was discovered to be effective in increasing awareness of the funds awarded. Accountability for bursary money and project decision integration, guaranteeing no disruptions to project performance. Furthermore, stakeholder capacity building emerged as a significant performance driver, providing stakeholders with the knowledge and information they need to efficiently complete distribution roles.

The study recommends that bursary programs begin by defining clear and quantifiable goals that are consistent with national education standards. This necessitates the participation of key stakeholders, such as education officials, community leaders, school administrators, parents, and students, in undertaking comprehensive needs assessments and planning. Such participatory techniques would guarantee that programs are tailored to the specific needs of the communities they serve, while also encouraging transparency and accountability.

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